

THE METRIC DIMENSION OF WHEEL GRAPH W_n & PARTITION DIMENSION OF GRAPH $K_s + \overline{K}_t$

Chard Aye Reyes Alova¹, Samuel Benny Dito², Kezya Samantha Sherryn³, Difa
Winanda Adliya^{4. a}, Moch Nabil Farras Dhiya^{4. b}

¹Faculty of Mathematics
College of Arts and Sciences
University of St. La Salle
ca.alova@usls.edu.ph

²Faculty of Teacher Training and Education
Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa University
2225180061@untirta.ac.id

³Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences
University of Indonesia
kezya.samantha@ui.ac.id

⁴Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences
Bandung Institute of Technology
^a16020100@students.itb.ac.id
^b16020147@students.itb.ac.id

1. ABSTRACT

In this paper, we determine and show the proof of the metric dimension of a wheel graph and the partition dimension of graph $F = K_s + \overline{K}_t$. The solution for the metric dimension is divided into four cases. If $n = 3$ or 6 , the metric dimension of wheel graph W_n is 3 . If $n = 4$ or 5 , the metric dimension of wheel graph W_n is 2 . If $n = 7$ or 8 , the metric dimension of wheel graph W_{n+5k} is $3 + 2k$ for k is a whole number. If $n = 9, 10$, or 11 , the metric dimension of wheel graph W_{n+5k} is $4 + 2k$ for k is a whole number. The solution for the partition dimension is divided into two cases. If $s \geq t$, the partition dimension of graph F is $s + 1$. If $s < t$, the partition dimension of graph F is t .

Keywords: metric dimension, wheel graph, partition dimension.

2. INTRODUCTION

When it comes to Applied Mathematics, we would be known that one of its branch is graph. There are many kinds of definitions of the graph and they can generalized simply as the discrete structures consisting of vertices and edges that connect these vertices. There are different kinds of graphs, depending on whether edges have directions, whether multiple edges can connect the same pair of vertices, and whether loops are allowed. Problems in almost every conceivable discipline can be solved using graph models. We can determine whether it is possible to walk down all the streets in a city without going down a street twice, and we can find the number of colors needed to color the regions of a map. Graphs also can be used to determine whether a circuit can be implemented on a planar circuit board. We can distinguish between two chemical compounds with the same molecular formula but different structures using graphs or we can even determine whether two computers are connected by a communications link using graph models of computer networks.

DEFINITION 1. Graph in General

A graph $G = (V,E)$ consists of V , a nonempty set of vertices (or nodes) and E , a set of edges. Each edge has either one or two vertices associated with it, called its endpoints. An edge is said to connect its endpoints.

Note that the set of of vertices V of a graph G may be infinite. A graph with an infinite vertex set or an infinite number of edges is called h a finite vertex set and a finite edge set is called a finite graph. To model a computer network that may contain multiple links between data centers, we need graphs that have more than one edge connecting the same pair of vertices which usually called as multigraphs.

Figure 2.1 A Computer Network with Multiple Links between Data Centers

DEFINITION 2. Cycle Graph

A cycle C_n where n is more than or equal to 3, consists of n vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n and edges $\{v_1, v_2\}, \{v_2, v_3\}, \dots, \{v_{n-1}, v_n\}$, and $\{v_n, v_1\}$. The examples are displayed below in Figure 2.2

Figure 2.2 The Cycles $C_3, C_4, C_5,$ and C_6

DEFINITION 3. Wheel Graph

We obtain a wheel W_n when we add an additional vertex to a cycle C_n , for n is more than or equal to 3 and connect this new vertex to each of the n vertices in C_n , by new edges. The examples of wheel graph are displayed below in Figure 3.

Figure 2.3 The Wheels $W_3, W_4, W_5,$ and W_6

DEFINITION 4. Metric Dimension

The metric dimension of a graph G , denoted by $\beta(G)$, is defined as the cardinality of a minimal subset of $V(G)$ having the property that each pair of vertices u, v there exists as w in S such that $d(w,u) \neq d(w,v)$.

THEOREM 1.1

- (i) $\beta(W_{1,3}) = \beta(W_{1,6}) = 3$
- (ii) $\beta(W_{1,4}) = \beta(W_{1,5}) = 2$
- (iii) $\beta(W_{1,x+5k}) = \begin{cases} 3 + 2k, & \text{when } x = 7 \text{ or } 8 \\ 4 + 2k, & \text{when } x = 9 \text{ or } 10 \text{ or } 11 \end{cases}$

DEFINITION 5. Complete Graph

A complete graph on n vertices, denoted by K_n is a simple graph that contains exactly one edge between each pair of distinct vertices. A simple graph for which there is at least one pair of distinct vertices not connected by an edge is called noncomplete. The examples are displayed below in Figure 4.

Figure 2.4 The Complete Graph $K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4, K_5,$ and K_6

DEFINITION 6. Partition Dimension

Partition dimension of a graph G , denoted by $pd(G)$, is defined as the smallest integer k such that G has a resolving k -partition.

THEOREM 1.2

- (i) Let G be a connected graph of order $n \geq 2$. Then $pd(G) = 2$ if and only if $G = P_n$
- (ii) Let G be a connected graph of order n . Then $pd(G) = n$ if and only if $G = K_n$
- (iii) Let G be a connected graph of order $n \geq 3$. Then $pd(G) = n-1$ if and only if G is one of the graphs $K_{1,n-1}, K_n - e,$ or $K_1 + (K_1 \cup K_{n-2})$

3. MAIN SECTION

(1) (Nilai 10) Let W_n be a wheel graph on $(n + 1)$ vertices, namely a graph obtained by connecting a vertex x to all vertices of a cycle on n vertices. Find the metric dimension of the wheel graph W_n , for $n \geq 3$. Prove your answer.

Answer:

According to **Theorem 1.1** (B. Shanmukha, B. Sooryanarayana, K.S. Harinath, 2002), we get the dimensions of some wheel graph W_n , $\dim(W_n)$, are of the following:

$$W_n = \begin{cases} 3, & n = 3 \text{ or } 6 \\ 2, & n = 4 \text{ or } 5 \end{cases}$$

$$W_{n+5k} = \begin{cases} 3 + 2k, & n = 7 \text{ or } 8 \\ 4 + 2k, & n = 9, 10, \text{ or } 11 \end{cases} \quad \text{for some } k \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$$

Proof. Let $G(V, E)$ connected and $G = W_n$.

Firstly, notice that the distance of any vertex that lies in the ring of the graph G to any other distinct vertex in G is either 1 or 2, where it is 1 if the other vertex is either exactly next to it or the other vertex is located in the center of G (center vertex). Also, notice that the distance of the center vertex to any other distinct vertex in G is exactly 1. Hence, we can conclude that X , the resolving set of G , will not contain the center vertex since the distance of any other vertex with respect to the center vertex is 1. Also, It is clear that since G is not the path P_n , or $G \neq P_n$, then $\dim(G) > 1$. Next, we will proof this theorem by dividing it into 6 cases as the following:

Case (i). $n = 3$ or 6

According to **Theorem 1.2.**, we know that $\dim(K_4) = 3$. Since W_3 is a complete graph K_4 , thus it is clear that $\dim(W_3) = \dim(K_4) = 3$.

Figure 3.1 W_6 graph

The resolving set X for $n \geq 6$ is an internally stable set as there is no two vertices $u \in X$ are adjacent and hence contains only vertices from the ring of the graph G . Hence, $\dim(W_6) > 2$. It will be proved that $\dim(W_6)$ is indeed can not be 2.

Suppose that $X_1 = \{v_1, v_3\}$ is the resolving set of G . But then from the figure above, notice that $r(v_2 | X_1) = r(v_6 | X_1) = (1, 1)$. Thus, X_1 is not the resolving set of G .

Next, let $X_2 = \{v_1, v_4\}$. But also notice that $r(v_3 | X_2) = r(v_5 | X_2) = (2, 1)$. Thus, X_2 is not the resolving set of G . And since G is a rotating graph, we have proved that X can not contain only 2 vertices from the graph G to be a resolving set.

Next, let $X_3 = \{v_1, v_3, v_5\}$. From the Figure 3.1, we get:

$$\begin{array}{lll} r(v_1 | X_3) = (0, 2, 2) & r(v_3 | X_3) = (2, 0, 2) & r(v_5 | X_3) = (2, 2, 0) \\ r(v_2 | X_3) = (1, 1, 2) & r(v_4 | X_3) = (2, 1, 1) & r(v_6 | X_3) = (1, 1, 1) \end{array}$$

Since $r(v_i | X_3) \neq r(v_j | X_3)$ for $i \neq j$ and any $v \in V(G)$, hence X_3 is the resolving set and also the minimum resolving set of G . Thus, $\dim(W_6) = 3$.

Case (ii). $n = 4$ or 5

Figure 3.2 W_4 graph

Figure 3.3 W_5 graph

Let $X_4 = \{v_1, v_2\}$. From the Figure 3.3 above, the representations of each vertices $v \in V(G)$ are:

$$\begin{array}{lll} r(v_1 | X_4) = (0, 1) & r(v_3 | X_4) = (1, 1) & r(v_5 | X_4) = (1, 2) \\ r(v_2 | X_4) = (1, 0) & r(v_4 | X_4) = (2, 1) & \end{array}$$

Since $r(v_i | X_4) \neq r(v_j | X_4)$ for $i \neq j$ and any vertices $v \in V(G)$, hence X_4 is the resolving set and also the minimum resolving set of G . Thus, $\dim(W_4) = 2$.

By doing similar steps as $n = 4$ for $n = 5$, we can then show that $r(v_i | X_4) \neq r(v_j | X_4)$ for $i \neq j$ and any vertices $v \in V(G)$. Thus, $\dim(W_5) = 2$.

Case (iv). $n = 7 + 5k$

Let $G_k = W_n$ for $n = 7 + 5k$. Firstly, we will show that $\dim(W) > 2(k + 1)$. Suppose that $\dim(G_k) = 2(k + 1)$, for some $k \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. Since the diameter of the wheel graph is 2, then the representations of every vertices $v \in V(G_k)$ are the combination of $\{0, 1, 2\}$. Thus,

- (a) No vertex in the ring of the graph G_k which contains more than two '1's in its representation with respect to some resolving set X of G_k .

- (b) There are exactly $2(k + 1)$ vertices which contain '0' in their representations since X contains $2(k + 1)$ vertices.
- (c) There are at most $2(k + 1)$ vertices which contain exactly one '1' in their representations with respect to X .
- (d) There are at most $(k + 1)$ vertices which contain exactly two '1's in their representations with respect to X .
- (e) There are at most 1 vertex which only contains '2' as the only element of its representation with respect to X .

Hence, there are at most $0 + 2(k + 1) + 2(k + 1) + (k + 1) + 1 = 6 + 5k < 7 + 5k$ in the ring of the graph G_k , which is clearly contradict with the value of n . Thus, $\dim(W_{7+5k}) \geq 3 + 2k$.

It will be proven that $\dim(W_{7+5k}) = 3 + 2k$, for some $k \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ by mathematical induction.

- (1) Check for $k = 0$.

Figure 3.4 W_7 graph

Let $X_0 = \{v_1, v_3, v_5\}$.

From the figure above, it is clear that every vertices $v \in V(G_0)$ have distinct representations with respect to X_0 . Thus, for $k = 0$, $\dim(W_7) = 3$, which is true.

- (2) Assume that for $k = t \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$, $\dim(W_{7+5t}) = 3 + 2t$.

- (3) It will be proven that (2) is true for $k = t + 1$.

Let $G_{t+1} = W_n$ for $n = 7 + 5t$ and $X_t = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_{3+2t}\}$ be the minimum resolving set of G_t . Notice that since X_t is the minimum resolving set of G_t which contains W_{7+5k} elements, more than half of the vertices $v \in V(G_t)$ do not construct X_t .

Let $V' = V(G) - X_t = \{v'_1, v'_2, v'_3, \dots, v'_{4+3t}\}$, where all vertices $v' \in V'$ is not an element of X_t . Hence, there is at least 2 vertices v'_i and v'_{i+1} for all $1 \leq i \leq 3 + 2t$,

which lies between v_j and v_{j+1} for all $1 \leq j \leq 2 + 2t$, such that $d(v'_i, v_j) = d(v'_{i+1}, v_{j+1}) = 1$.

Let X_t' be the unordered set of X_t , $\{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{3+2t}\}$. Then, we can write the representations of each v'_i, v'_{i+1}, v_j , and v_{j+1} with respect to X_t' as:

$$r(v'_1 | X_t') = (0, 2, 2)$$

$$r(v'_{i+1} | X_t') = (0, 2, 2)$$

$$r(v_j | X_t') = (0, 2, 2)$$

$$r(v_{j+1} | X_t') = (0, 2, 2)$$

Since $v'_i \neq v'_{i+1}$ and $v_j \neq v_{j+1}$, it is clear that both v'_i and v'_{i+1} have distinct coordinates, and so does v_j and v_{j+1} .

Next, notice that G_{t+1} can be constructed by inserting 5 vertices $v'_{i,x}$ for all $1 \leq x \leq 5$ to G_t at suitable edges. It is clear that the 5 inserted vertices have the same representation with respect to X_t , and since $\max\{d(v, w) : w \in X_t\} = 2$, it is also clear that at least two inserted vertices (e.g. $v'_{i,2}$ and $v'_{i,4}$) have to be included in X_t such that all vertices $v \in V(G_t)$ has distinguishable representation and X_t is still the minimum resolving set of G_t . For clearer illustration, see the figures below.

Figure 3.5 G_{t+1} illustration

From Figure 3.5 above, observe that S_1 and S_2 form the same pattern as shown in Figure 3.4, which clearly have distinguishable representations as shown at (1). Hence, let $X_{t+1} = X_t \cup \{v'_{i,2}, v'_{i,4}\}$. By doing similar steps, it can be shown that $\dim(X_{t+1}) \geq 3 + 2(k + 1)$. Hence, X_{t+1} is the minimum revolving set for G_{t+1} . Thus, $\dim(G_{t+1}) = 3 + 2(k + 1)$.

Case (v). $n = 8 + 5k$

Let $G_k = W_n$ for $n = 8 + 5k$. Then, notice that from the Figure 3.5, we see that if we inserted one more vertex $v'_{i,0}$ at suitable edge (e.g. between v_j and $v'_{i,2}$) as illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 3.6 G_{t+1} illustration

From the Figure 3.6 above, it is suffice to show that v'_i , $v'_{i,0}$, and $v'_{i,1}$ have distinct representations to prove that X_{t+1} the minimum resolving set of G_k . But then, it is clear that those three vertices have distinct representations since it has the same pattern as Figure 3.3. Hence, every vertices $v \in V(G_k)$ would still have distinct representations with respect to X_{t+1} and implies that X_{t+1} is the minimum resolving set for G_k and G_k . Thus, $\dim(G_k) = 3 + 2k$.

Case (vi). $n = 9, 10, \text{ or } 11$

Let G_m , $G_{m'}$, and $G_{m''}$ be the wheel graphs W_n for $n = 9 + 5k$, $n = 10 + 5k$, and $n = 11 + 5k$, respectively. It is not hard to notice that as we inserted another 1-3 vertice(s) even with suitable edges to G_k to construct G_m , $G_{m'}$, and $G_{m''}$, X_t is no longer a resolving set for all G_m , $G_{m'}$, and $G_{m''}$. Hence, we have to add another vertex v to X_t , such that $X_m = X_t \cup \{v\}$, is a resolving set for all G_m , $G_{m'}$, and $G_{m''}$.

Notice that as we pick the suitable vertex v to be included in X_m , the same pattern which appeared in Figure 3.5 appeared again for $n = 9$ and the same pattern which appeared in Figure 3.6 appeared again for $n = 10$ and 11 . It implies that X_t is indeed a resolving set for all G_m , $G_{m'}$, and $G_{m''}$. Since X_t has the minimum elements such that all $x \in V(G_m)$, $y \in V(G_{m'})$, and $z \in V(G_{m''})$ have distinct representations, then it can be concluded that $\dim(G_m) = \dim(G_{m'}) = \dim(G_{m''}) = 4 + 2k$.

By the cases (i) to (vi), the theorem is proven. ■

(2) (Nilai 10) Let $F = K_s + \overline{K}_t$, where $s, t \geq 2$. Determine the partition dimension of graph F . Prove your answer.

Answer:

Given $F = K_s + \overline{K}_t$, where $s, t \geq 2$. The partition dimension of graph F , denoted by $pd(F)$ is given by:

$$pd(F) = \begin{cases} s + 1, & s \geq t \\ t, & s < t \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let $V(K_s) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_s\}$ and $V(\overline{K}_t) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}$ where $K_s + \overline{K}_t = F$ and $s, t \geq 2$. Then, we connect the vertices of graphs K_s and \overline{K}_t to form graph F . Hence, we have $E(F) = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_t\}$ where $a_n = (u_i, u_j)$ or (u_i, v_k) for an edge a_n with endpoints u_i and u_j or v_k for $1 \leq i, j \leq s, i \neq j$, and $1 \leq k \leq t$. By simple observation, we then notice the following:

- $d(u_1, u_2) = d(u_1, u_3) = \dots = d(u_1, u_s) = 1$, which also applies for u_2, u_3, \dots, u_s .
- $d(u_1, v_2) = d(u_1, v_2) = \dots = d(u_1, v_t) = 1$, which also applies for u_2, u_3, \dots, u_s .
- $d(u_1, u_1) = d(u_2, u_2) = \dots = d(u_s, u_s)$, which also applies for $(v_1, v_1) = d(v_2, v_2) = \dots = d(v_t, v_t) = 0$.
- $d(v_1, v_2) = d(v_1, v_3) = \dots = d(v_1, v_t) = 2$, which also applies for v_2, v_3, \dots, v_t .

In order to determine the partition dimension of graph F , we consider the 3 cases:

Case (i). For $s > t$:

By our observation arguments, we assume that all vertices $v \in V(\overline{K}_t)$ can be paired with exactly one vertex $u \in V(K_s)$, and the remaining vertices $u \in V(K_s)$ will be isolatedly partitioned. And let that every vertices u and v that are paired have the same index m and will form a partition S_m , for $1 \leq m \leq t$.

Let $\Pi_1 = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_t, \dots, S_s\}$ where there are s elements in Π_1 .

Figure 3.8 F rough illustration for $s > t$ with s partitions

Note: not all vertices have complete edges (only u_2) to make the illustration easier to observe.

But then, notice that for $m = 1$ as shown at the Figure 3.8 above:

$$r(u_1 | \Pi_1) = (0, 1, \dots, 1, \dots, 1)$$

$$r(v_1 | \Pi_1) = (0, 1, \dots, 1, \dots, 1)$$

Clearly, $r(u_1 | \Pi_1) = r(v_1 | \Pi_1)$, which also apply to all vertices u_m, v_m that are paired in the same partition. This cannot be the case. Hence, it is clear that there must be at least one partition which contains only one vertex from $V(\bar{K}_t)$, such that every vertices u, v have distinct representation with respect to some partition set Π . Hence, the range value of m has to be updated to $1 \leq m \leq t - 1$. Then, we will have this construction of graph F :

Figure 3.9 F rough illustration for $s > t$ with $(s + 1)$ partitions

Note: not all vertices have complete edges (only u_2) to make the illustration easier to observe.

Let $\Pi_2 = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_t, \dots, S_s, S_{s+1}\}$ where there are $(s + 1)$ elements of Π_2 .

To prove that every vertices $u, v \in V(F)$ have distinct representation with respect to Π_2 , it is suffice to show that for some specific value of m , then the vertices u_m, v_m that are paired in the same partition have distinguishable representation since F is a rotating graph and every isolated partition which only contain one vertex clearly have different representations.

Let $m = 3$. Hence, we get that:

$$r(u_1|\Pi_2) = (0, 1, \dots, 1, \dots, 1, 1)$$

$$r(v_1|\Pi_2) = (0, 1, \dots, 1, \dots, 2, 1)$$

Since $r(u_m|\Pi_2) \neq r(v_m|\Pi_2)$ for $1 \leq m \leq t-1$, and it is clear that every isolated partition which only contain one vertex have different representations, it is clear that Π_2 is the resolving partition and also the minimum resolving set of F for $s > t$. Thus,

$$pd(F) = s + 1.$$

Case (ii). For $s = t$:

By doing the same steps as the previous case, which are pairing every vertices $u \in V(\overline{K}_t)$ with exactly one vertex $v \in V(K_s)$, except for one vertex u, v from each K_s and \overline{K}_t , letting every vertices u and v that are paired have the same index m and will form a partition S_m , for $1 \leq m \leq t - 1$, and show that for some specific value of m , then $r(u_m|\Pi_3) \neq r(v_m|\Pi_3)$.

Let $\Pi_3 = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_t, \dots, S_s, S_{s+1}\}$ where there are $(s + 1)$ elements of Π_3 .

Hence, by looking at Figure 3.9, for $m = 3$, we get:

$$r(u_1|\Pi_3) = (0, 1, \dots, 1, \dots, 1, 1)$$

$$r(v_1|\Pi_3) = (0, 1, \dots, 1, \dots, 2, 1)$$

By the same arguments as the previous case, it is clear that Π_3 is the resolving partition and also the minimum resolving set of F for $s = t$. Thus,

$$pd(F) = s + 1 = t + 1.$$

Case (iii). For $s < t$:

Since we know that there can't be vertices from \overline{K}_t to be in the same partition and the maximum elements of partition S can only contain exactly one vertex from each of $V(K_s)$ and $V(\overline{K}_t)$. Then, by doing the same steps as the previous cases, which are by pairing

every vertices $u \in V(\overline{K}_t)$ with exactly one vertex $v \in V(K_s)$, except for one vertex u, v from each K_s and \overline{K}_t , letting every vertices u and v that are paired have the same index n and will form a partition S_n , for $1 \leq n \leq s$, and show that for some specific value of n , then $r(u_n | \Pi_4) \neq r(v_n | \Pi_4)$.

We assume there are t partitions.

Let $\Pi_4 = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_s, \dots, S_{t-1}, S_t\}$.

Figure 3.10 F rough illustration for $s < t$ with t partitions

Note: not all vertices have complete edges (only u_1) to make the illustration easier to observe.

Hence, by looking at Figure 3.10 above, for $n = 3$, we get:

$$r(u_1 | \Pi_4) = (0, 1, \dots, 1, \dots, 1, 1)$$

$$r(v_1 | \Pi_4) = (0, 1, \dots, 1, \dots, 2, 2)$$

By the same arguments as the two previous cases, it is clear that Π_4 is the resolving partition and also the minimum resolving set of F for $s < t$. Thus,

$$pd(F) = t.$$

By cases (i), (ii), and (iii), we then have proved our answer. ■

4. References

- [1] Shanmukha, B., Sooryanarayana, B., & Harinath, K. S. (2002). Metric dimension of wheels. *Far East J. Appl. Math*, 8(3), 217-229.
- [2] Rosen, Kenneth H., Seventh Edition Discrete Mathematics and Its Applications, Graph and Graph Models, Graph Terminology and Special Types of Graphs, 641-655.
- [3] G. Chartrand, E. Salehi and P. Zhang, The partition dimension of a graph, *Aequationes Math.*, 59, 45–54 (2000).